

TABLE 2—COMPARATIVE STUDY OF SOME CALORIMETRIC METHODS FOR NICKEL USING DIFFERENT REAGENTS

Reagents	$\lambda_{\max}$ nm	Molar absorptivity $\text{dm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$	Sensitivity $\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$
Dimethylglyoxime + oxidising agent ^a	445	1.89×10^4	0.0042
Diethyldithiocarbamate ^a	325	3.26×10^4	0.0018
o-Mercaptoacetacetanilide + 7-picolins ^b	615	5.21×10^3	0.05
Rubeanic acid + quinoline ^c	390	8.46×10^3	0.0058
Diphenylcarbazone + pyridine ^d	590	9.62×10^4	0.00061

^aRef. 9. ^bRef. 10. ^cRef. 11. ^dPresent work.

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References

1. F. J. WELCHER, "Organic Analytical Reagents", D. Von Nostrand, London, 1955, Vol. III, p. 430.
2. H. K. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 182.
3. H. K. DAS and K. G. KAIMAL, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 668.
4. FEIGL and A. F. LEDERER, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 1924, **45**, 115.
5. S. BALZ and E. V. DALEN, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1963, **29**, 466.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th. ed., ELBS, London, 1978, p. 479.
7. P. JOB, *Compt. Rend.*, 1925, **180**, 928, *Ann. Chim. (Paris)*, 1928, **9**, 113.
8. A. E. HARVEY, JR. and D. L. MANNING, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
9. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd ed., Interscience, New York, 1959, p. 669.
10. A. K. DAS and J. DAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 488.
11. M. B. SAHA and A. K. CHAKRABURTY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, **60**, 281.

Some Titrimetric Applications of N-Iodophthalimide in Aqueous Acetic Acid Medium

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RECENTLY, N-chlorophthalimide and N-bromophthalimide have been developed as better and stabler oxidimetric titrants than most other oxidants of similar type^{1,2}. A search through the literature has revealed that their iodine analogue, viz. N-iodophthalimide (NIP) has not been used as an oxidimetric titrant so far although it has been used in clinical pharmacology³. Therefore, we thought it would be interesting to explore the possibility of employing NIP as an oxidant for titrations in aqueous acetic acid medium. In this communication, we report the results of determination of 37 reductants of diverse types using NIP as the titrant in aqueous acetic acid medium.

Experimental

N-Iodophthalimide (NIP) was prepared by iodinating phthalimide using freshly prepared ICl as

per the literature method⁴. Phthalimide (15.0 g) was dissolved in minimum quantity of 10 M potassium hydroxide (20 ml). The solution was cooled to 5° in an ice-salt-bath and a previously cooled solution of ICl (20 ml) dissolved in acetonitrile (50 ml) was added slowly in small portions with stirring. Care was taken to keep the temperature of the reaction mixture always below 5°. The greenish yellow crystals of NIP formed were collected and washed with cold water-acetonitrile mixture (1 : 1, v/v) and finally with cold dry acetonitrile. The solid sample was dried in vacuum over phosphorus pentoxide, the yield being about (85%), m.p. 225° (lit. 226°) (Found : I, 46.52. calcd. ; I, 46.32%). The purity of NIP was checked by an iodometric method, in which a known weight of the sample (0.05 g) was allowed to react with excess of potassium iodide (0.5 g) in acetic acid medium and the liberated iodine was titrated with standard thiosulphate.

NIP was found to be sparingly soluble in water undergoing hydrolysis with the liberation of iodine, and soluble in acetic acid (solubility, 10.2 g/kg at 30°). Approximately 0.05 N (~0.025 M) solution of NIP was prepared in anhydrous acetic acid (500 ml) by dissolving dry NIP (3.4 g) and kept in an amber coloured bottle; such a solution being reasonably stable to meet the requirements for an ideal titrant for use in non-aqueous media. The stock solution of NIP was standardised iodometrically as usual before use.

The following 37 reductants were chosen for titrations using NIP : As^{III}, sulphite, ascorbic acid, hydroquinone, hydrazine, benzhydrazide, isoniazid, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide, thiosemicarbazide, thioacetamide, thiourea, aniline, phenol, oxine, anthranilic acid, oxinates of Mg^{II}, Al^{II}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and La^{III}, anthranilates of Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Pb^{II}, and thiosemicarbazides of Mn^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}, Hg^{II} and Pb^{II}. The metal oxinates, anthranilates and thiosemicarbazides were prepared by the literature methods⁵⁻⁸. Standard solutions of all the 37 reductants listed above were prepared in appropriate solvents as described earlier^{9,9}. The strengths of these reductant solutions were checked by standard methods^{9,10}.

Direct visual titrations were unsuccessful for anthranilic acid and its metal derivatives, and thiosemicarbazide and its metal derivatives. All the other reductants were determined by direct visual titration using quinoline yellow or amaranth as indicator. The usual procedures were used for both direct and excess-back titrations.

Results and Discussion

The results of the titrations are presented in Table 1 (direct titrations) and Table 2 (excess-back-titrations). During the reaction with the reductant, NIP is reduced to phthalimide,

where, $R=C_8H_4O_2$. The formation of phthalimide is confirmed by characterising the product by spectral analysis and melting point.

TABLE 1—DIRECT VISUAL TITRATIONS USING N-IODOPHTHALIMIDE

Reductant*	Range of reductant taken m mol	Standard deviation μ mol	Coefficient of variation	Mean error %
As ^{III}	0.23-0.45	1.8	0.17	0.25
Sb ^{III}	0.28-0.55	1.2	0.11	0.10
Sulphite	0.41-0.80	1.5	0.15	0.12
Ascorbic acid	0.14-0.29	2.7	0.27	0.36
Hydroquinone	0.43-0.82	2.4	0.24	0.16
Hydrazine	0.20-0.40	1.8	0.18	0.15
Benzhydrazide	0.15-0.30	2.1	0.20	0.19
Isoniazid	0.25-0.52	1.9	0.19	0.15
Phenylhydrazine	0.15-0.31	1.9	0.19	0.17
Semicarbazide	0.25-0.55	1.3	0.13	0.21
Thioacetamide	0.06-0.12	3.0	0.31	0.25
Thiourea	0.12-0.25	1.4	0.14	0.17
Aniline	0.19-0.38	1.9	0.19	0.16
Phenol	0.14-0.28	2.3	0.23	0.18
Oxine	0.18-0.40	1.8	0.18	0.15
Mg ^{II} oxinate	0.14-0.29	3.0	0.30	0.28
Al ^{III} oxinate	0.05-0.12	2.9	0.30	0.24
Mn ^{II} oxinate	0.05-0.10	1.2	0.12	0.12
Co ^{II} oxinate	0.10-0.20	3.1	0.32	0.23
Ni ^{II} oxinate	0.15-0.30	1.7	0.17	0.11
Zn ^{II} oxinate	0.09-0.18	3.2	0.32	0.30
Cd ^{II} oxinate	0.11-0.22	2.2	0.23	0.20
La ^{II} oxinate	0.06-0.12	3.0	0.30	0.20

* Amaranth indicator used for oxine and metal oxinates, and quinoline yellow for all other reductants.

TABLE 2—EXCESS-BACK-TITRATIONS USING N-IODOPHTHALIMIDE

Reductant*	Range of reductant taken m mol	Standard deviation μ mol	Coefficient of variation	Mean error %
Anthranilic acid	0.20-0.40	2.0	0.20	0.11
Mn ^{II} anthranilate	0.06-0.12	1.5	0.15	0.20
Co ^{II} anthranilate	0.08-0.15	2.9	0.29	0.28
Ni ^{II} anthranilate	0.05-0.11	2.6	0.26	0.28
Zn ^{II} anthranilate	0.07-0.22	3.0	0.31	0.26
Cd ^{II} anthranilate	0.05-0.12	2.9	0.30	0.26
Pb ^{II} anthranilate	0.02-0.05	3.2	0.32	0.23
Thiosemicarbazide	0.11-0.23	2.2	0.23	0.21
Mn ^{II} thiosemicarbazide	0.02-0.05	2.9	0.30	0.29
Ni ^{II} thiosemicarbazide	0.03-0.07	2.7	0.27	0.26
Zn ^{II} thiosemicarbazide	0.05-0.10	1.7	0.18	0.16
Cd ^{II} thiosemicarbazide	0.05-0.11	1.8	0.18	0.12
Hg ^{II} thiosemicarbazide	0.01-0.20	2.3	0.23	0.18
Pb ^{II} thiosemicarbazide	0.05-0.11	1.9	0.19	0.17

* A period of 15 min required for all the compounds.

All the reductants can be conveniently determined by the present reagent in aqueous acetic acid medium (50%, v/v). Addition of sodium acetate (0.5 g) is found essential for all the direct titrations, and the function of sodium acetate is to act as catalyst for the reactions. Addition of potassium bromide (0.5 g) is needed for those systems which undergo bromination rather than oxidation during

titration. Thus presence of potassium bromide is needed for aniline, phenol, oxine, metal oxinates, anthranilic acid and metal anthranilates, while for all other systems direct reactions with NIP are successful. The function of added bromide is to produce bromine *in situ* by the reaction with NIP. This bromine will brominate these reductants as usual. For excess-back-titrations, a period of 15 min is needed for all the systems.

The results indicate that the present reagent is capable of determining all the 37 reductants (Tables 1 and 2) with high degree of accuracy and precision. All the reductants undergo their usual oxidation schemes reported elsewhere. In conformity with their oxidation schemes, 2 equivalents of NIP are consumed per mole of arsenic(III), antimony(III), sulphite, ascorbic acid and hydroquinone; 4 equivalents for hydrazine, benzhydrazide, isoniazide, phenylhydrazine, semicarbazide and oxine; 6 equivalents for aniline, phenol and anthranilic acid; 8 equivalents for thioacetamide, thiourea and oxinates of dipositive metal ions; 10 equivalents for thiosemicarbazide; 12 equivalents for oxinates of tripositive metal ions and anthranilates of dipositive metal ions; and 20 equivalents for metal thiosemicarbazides.

In conclusion, the present reagent is capable of determining a number of compounds of diverse types including complexes. Majority of these reductants studied could be determined by direct titration method. The present studies indicate that NIP is a potential oxidimetric titrant for several determinations.

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References

1. N. JAYASREE and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1985, **32**, 1067.
2. C. MOHANADAS and P. INDRASENAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1984, **23**, 869.
3. L. JIROUSEK and M. SOODAK, *J. Pharmacol. Exptl. Ther.*, 1974, **191**, 341.
4. R. SOUNDARARAJAN, S. KRISHNAMOORTHY, V. S. SRINIVASAN and T. R. BALASUBRAMANIAN, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1983, **255**, 295.
5. O. DUVAL, "Inorganic Thermogravimetric Analysis", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1963.
6. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Inorganic Quantitative Analysis", Longmanns, London, 1964.
7. N. M. M. GOWDA, A. S. A. MOORTHY and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 5.
8. N. M. M. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, **44**, 747.
9. P. INDRASENAN and M. P. RADHAMMA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 729.
10. I. M. KOLTHOFF and R. BELCHER, "Volumetric Analysis", Interscience, New York, 1957, Vol. III.